

Features of Genetic Mutations of Tuberculosis Mycobacteria at the Current Stage

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Abstract: It is known that mutations in several loci of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* genome, including *katG*, *inhA*, *kasA*, *ahpC*, *ndh*, *nat* and *mshA* mutations play a major role. Most of the studies are based on the detection of mutations using DNA sequencing, hybridization on DNA chips, PCR, etc. [Tomasz Yagielski, 2015].

Key words: tuberculosis, quality of microbiological studies, drug resistance, multidrug-resistant tuberculosis, widely drug-resistant tuberculosis.

According to scientific publications, the drug molecule is activated inside the microbial cell under the action of catalase-peroxidase enzyme (*katG* gene). Mutations in the *KatG* gene cause a 50% decrease in enzyme activity, which is the most common cause of resistance. The genetic studies carried out fully explain the relationship between catalase activity of mycobacteria and resistance to isoniazid. These studies confirm the important role of *KatG* in the biological activity of isoniazid, confirming that it is a prodrug [Savinova, 2017].

In addition, after entering INH after a series of metabolic processes, the pharmacologically active derivative forms adducts with NAD⁺ or NADP⁺ coenzyme molecules, acts as an inhibitor of the enzyme involved in the biosynthesis of nucleic acids, as well as mycolic acids. Components of the cell wall of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* [Timmins G. _ S., Deretik V., 2006] studied mutations in the *katG* gene in 46 museum strains of isoniazid-resistant *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. The most common mutation is a substitution at codon 315, which is found in 74% of MDR *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* strains. Researchers believe that the presence of mutations in this codon may be a predictor of INH resistance. The authors stated that 87.5% of the 16 mutations identified at the level of the *katG* nucleotide sequence resulted in amino acid changes in the *KatG* polypeptide chain [Yagielski. T. _ and others al., 2013].

In addition, mutations in codon 315 of the *katG* gene were noted in many scientific publications. Furthermore, serine to threonine substitutions account for 95% of all *katG* 315 mutations [Marwa Seifert, 2015].

Materials and methods. *KatG* mutations are associated with a wide range of isoniazid resistance, from the most commonly tested concentrations above 0.2 and 1 mg/L in solid medium and 0.1 and 0.4 mg/L in liquid culture medium. high. Regarding the molecular mechanisms, many authors, in addition to *katG* mutations, isoniazid resistance is caused by mutations in the *inhA* promoter region. This phenomenon leads to overexpression of the isoniazid target (*InhA*), which requires high doses of the drug to achieve complete inhibition. The results of many studies show that mutations in the *inhA* promoter region lead to low-level phenotypic resistance, as well as resistance to ethionamide and prothionamide [Böttger. E. _ C., 2011; Vilchez C., 2014].

Comparative analysis of complete genomic sequences revealed differences between strains at the level of single nucleotides (Single-Nucleotide Polymorphisms-SNP) and longer fragments (Large Sequence

Polymorphisms-LSP). The use of SNP and LSP analysis has been proposed for family-specific typing and study of mutations leading to lymph node formation. Practice shows that the clinical presentation of tuberculosis caused by the indicated genotype is very unfavorable [6].

The history of the discovery of representatives of the Beijing family, originally known as the W-strain, begins in the 90s of the last century. In earlier scientific publications, Beijing genotype strains were divided into 4 groups: endemic, in which no correlation between genotype and DR was found; epidemic, associated with DR; A non-DR outbreak; rare or undetected [2].

Distribution on the basis of genotyping data, *identification of 9 genetic families of Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, of which strains of the Beijing genetic family are the most common in China, Japan, Southeast Asia and the CIS countries, with a prevalence of 30 to 70%. According to the SITVIT database, genotype strains are characterized by spoligotype SIT 1 (Spoligotype International Type), which is determined by the presence of 9 out of 43 gaps in the DR locus - from 35 to 43 [Demay et al., 2012; Liu L., 2018].

Representatives of this genotype are divided into atypical/ancient and typical/modern strains, and modern strains are characterized by the deletion of RD150 and/or RD142, as well as the presence of a repetitive IS6110 element in the NTF region. Brossier F. et al. 2014].

The increased interest in the Beijing genotype is due to the fact that it has the ability to spread quickly, has a fast progressive course, causes disseminated forms of tuberculosis, causes active release of bacteria, and has a high mutation rate; XDR and MDR often. Found among strains of Beijing genotype.

Zhdanova SN and others. [2018] report the discovery of non-native isolates of Beijing BL7 (MIT 642) and S (MIT 256) genotypes in South America, Bulgaria and Romania, which are of epidemic importance in North Asia and a wider area. Neighboring regions of Asia and Europe, as well as determining their role in shaping the high level of MDR prevalence.

Vasilyeva NR [2016] conducted a clinical and epidemiological analysis of 85 cases of pulmonary tuberculosis with XDR *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. Their strains have been identified to 7 spoligotypes of genetic families: Beijing (81.2%), LAM (14.1%) and Ural (4.7%). Among the examined patients infected with *Beijing strains of Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, men with a tendency to bad habits prevailed; Places of infection were not only apartments, but also penitentiaries. This group is characterized by different clinical forms of lung damage with a predominance of fibrous-cavernous tuberculosis and a significant proportion of patients who delay treatment.

Beijing genotype in Europe is characterized by a significant diversity in the number of identified strains of this genetic family. For the Russian Federation, Ukraine, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Kyrgyzstan, Azerbaijan, Latvia, Estonia, Armenia, Georgia, the share of Beijing genotype was about 50%. At the same time, its share did not exceed 10% in Poland, Finland, Bulgaria and Turkey. The uneven distribution of the Beijing genotype in a number of European countries is only a manifestation of factors related to certain countries [Sinkov VV, 2012; Surkova LK, et al., 2016].

Among the strains circulating in Belarus, mutations were most often observed in the *katG* gene - codon 315. At the same time, MDR-causing mutations in *Mycobacterium tuberculosis isolates isolated from patients were more frequently detected in codon 315 of katG. gene*, less often in codons 15 and 8 of the *inhA* gene [Bostonabad ZS et al., 2007].

using VNTR typing of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis isolates* isolated from 46 patients with pulmonary tuberculosis living in Astana (Kazakhstan) showed a predominance of Beijing genotype up to 70% among isolated isolates . The study identified 23 different genetic profiles that identified mutations in codon 315 of the *KatG* gene and mutations in codon 531 of the *rpoB* gene with amplification of a fragment containing codon 315 of the *katG* gene and a fragment containing codon 531 of *rpoB. gen*.

Dymova MA et al., [2011] note that the sample contains resistant and susceptible isolates of the Beijing family, and this family has no association with DR, which indicates the individual characteristics of these isolates circulating in a certain area.

According to experts from Kazakhstan, evaluation of the spectrum of *katG* gene mutations, *fabGinA*, *oxyR-ahpC* and *rpoB* promoter regions, resistance of *tuberculosis mycobacteria* to isoniazid and rifampicin, identification of genetic families of 103 multi-resistant *Mycob clinical isolates. Tuberculosis*, which is widespread in Kazakhstan, was carried out using the Sanger method and spoligotyping. The results showed that mutations in codon 531 of Ser→Leu *rpoB* gene (87.4%) and codon 315 of Ser→Thr *katG* gene (97%) were predominant among the isolates, conferring resistance to rifampicin and isoniazid. More than 80% of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* strains with MDR are classified as the most virulent and widespread Beijing genotype in the world [Akhmetova AJ et al., 2019].

Khromova PA and others. [2017] performed a bioinformatic search, designed primers and TaqMan probes to detect *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* DNA. CC1 and CC2-W148 subtypes of the Beijing genotype, as well as the Ural genotype in different isolates using real-time PCR. The sensitivity of the CC1, CC2-W148 and Ural tests compared to the GeneXpert PCR analyzer was 91%, 106% and 81%, respectively. Specificity was 100% in all cases. In parallel studies, samples with DNA of the CC2-W148 genotype were more likely to be positive for rifampicin resistance mutations by GeneXpert compared to other genotypes. However, the detection of the CC2-W148 strain in the patient was often accompanied by inconsistencies in the results. The obtained results showed the possibility of using the genotype of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and patient for early prognosis of MDR/XDR development and other complications during primary screening stages of newly diagnosed patients.

Currently, the development of whole-genome sequencing and comparative genomics techniques is helping to fuel efforts to address the challenges posed. These methods allow, for example, the assessment of microevolutionary changes in the genome leading to the development of DR and the study of the macroevolution of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* associated with the emergence of strains that characterize population success. Shitikov E. _ et al., [2012; 2014].

Among 140 strains of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, a search was made for relationships between the genotype of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, the clinical course of the disease and the resistance of the strain to antibiotics. According to the results of genotyping using the MIRU-VNTR method and the results of the detection of the deletion polymorphism in the 207 region of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* genome, 88% of the isolates were identified, a significant part of which belonged to and related to the Beijing family of epidemic importance. with MDR. Among the strains of this family, 11 subtypes have been identified, 2/3 of which are the most common subpopulations M2 and M11. A higher level of primary drug resistance has been reported among Beijing strains than among representatives of other genetic families [Lats AA et al., 2011].

Mycobacterium tuberculosis genomic DNA samples using the experimental TB-TEST kit. This method is based on the use of oligonucleotide biochip technology and allows to identify the most common genotypes and mutations responsible for the formation of resistance to the main anti-tuberculosis drugs - rifampicin, isoniazid, ethambutol, fluoroquinolones, aminoglycosides and capreomycin. As a result, resistance profiles were obtained and genotypes were determined for all samples. The developed "TB-TEST" system is a priority for use in clinical laboratory diagnostics [Bespyatykh Yu.A. et al., 2013].

Pasechnik OA et al. [2018] presented the results of the assessment of the prevalence of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* in the Omsk Region. The prevalence of KDR was 13.6 per 100,000 population. Among those infected with CDR are young people aged 25-44 (63.2%), men (80.9%), unemployed (75.6%), and the disease has lasted for more than 3 years (57.0%). constituted the majority. pulmonary

tuberculosis (69.2%), infected with HIV (31.8%). In 10.1% of patients with XDR, resistance to seven main and backup anti-tuberculosis drugs was detected at the same time. It was concluded that it is necessary to optimize approaches to the organization of additional measures for the prevention of drug-resistant tuberculosis.

The same authors presented the results of the study of molecular genetic characteristics of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* strains in other scientific works [Pasechnik OA et al., 2017]. In the Omsk region of the Russian Federation, with the circulation MDR. The prevalence rate of tuberculosis was 269.2 per 100,000 population. In 48.0% of newly diagnosed patients, the causative agent was found to be resistant to anti-tuberculosis drugs. In the composition of DR, MDR made up 57%, the share of XDR increased from 2.5% to 7.0%. The population of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* with MDR is heterogeneous and is represented by strains of different genetic families - Beijing, LAM, S, Haarlem, Uganda.

In addition, in the same region, other authors studied 325 strains of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* isolated from patients with tuberculosis. Among 204 (62.7%) *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* strains of the Beijing genotype, 176 (86.3%) strains were modern sublineages of the 94-32 (60.7%) and B0/W148 (25.0%) clusters. Among the 94-32 clusters, 13 (10.5%) strains of the CAO group were found. Ancient Beijing subline RD181[+] and RD181[-] strains were detected in 3.4% (7/204) and 10.3% (21/204) of cases, respectively. All Beijing RD181[+] strains had the SIT269 spoligo profile. Most strains of the old subline are represented by MIRU types - MIT135 and MIT642. In the population of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* of the Beijing genotype in the Omsk region of Western Siberia, modern subline strains prevailed, the prevalence of ancient strains of this genotype (13.7%). B0/W148, 94-32 strains of the modern subline of CAO clusters and strains of the ancient Beijing subline were characterized by a high level of MDR [Vyazovaya AA et al., 2020].

The population structure of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* was assessed using MIRU-12 and MIRU-24 genotyping methods. 283 strains isolated from treated individuals were studied. The prevalence of pandemic subtypes Beijing MIT17 and MIT16, as well as Beijing MIT642 (24.5% or 46/188), was determined, their predominance is specific only to the study area. Isolates of this strain are common among all groups of patients with pulmonary tuberculosis, with the predominant formation of MDR in the chronic course of the disease [Zhdanova SN et al., 2014].

In the Republic of Moldova, information was obtained describing tuberculosis with DR and MDR, XDR, which allows to increase the effectiveness of treatment by determining the effective doses of injection drugs (Cm, Km, Am) based on drug concentration. in culture when determining resistance. Depending on the nature of resistance, individual treatment regimens are developed and certain treatment periods are determined [Sain DO et al., 2015].

Andreevskaya SN and others. [2020] identified the incidence of IR-TB in a modern population, characterized the genetic determinants of phenotypic susceptibility and isoniazid resistance of members of this *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* group on representative material. The incidence of IR-TB accounted for 12% of all detected TB cases. *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* with IR isoniazid mono-resistant (45%) and multi-resistant (resistant to 2-6 anti-tuberculosis drugs), and resistance to isoniazid occurred as a result of mutations in the *katG* gene, which led to a high level of resistance. Based on the analysis of our observations, the importance of developing new simple molecular tests for detection of resistance to rifampicin and isoniazid is emphasized.

According to the results of spoligotyping, representatives of the Beijing genetic family (spoligotypes SIT1 and SIT190) prevailed among *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* strains of patients in the Leningrad region of the Russian Federation, and their share exceeded 56.3% (27 of 48). In 1999-2004. 76.5% in 2010-2014 (52 out of 68). The share of other genotypes - LAM and T strains decreased from 16.7 and

12.5% to 10.3 and 2.9%, respectively. The proportion of MDR in the studied subpopulations of the Beijing genotype was almost unchanged (88.9 and 86.5%). The largest clusters MIT16 (223325153533) and MIT17 (223325173533) included 25 (48.1%) and 21 (40.4%) strains of the Beijing genotype [Vyazovaya AA et al., 2017].

Samsonov K.Yu in his research. and others. [2020] included 82 patients over 18 years of age with newly diagnosed pulmonary tuberculosis in the remission phase. In the group of patients with an effective course of chemotherapy, carriers of the G allele and T/G genotype at the rs6707530 locus of the *FN1* gene are more common. At the same time, the T/T genotype and the T allele predominated in patients with permanent destruction of lung tissue after an intensive phase of chemotherapy.

It should be noted that the DOTS program was implemented on the initiative of the WHO in 1998 based on the tuberculosis treatment strategy directly observed in Central Asian countries. It covered three areas south of the Aral Sea, was implemented by the humanitarian medical aid organization Doctors Without Borders, and ended in 2003. By 2002, more than 8,000 patients were registered and treated under DOTS in the Republic of Karakalpakstan (RKK), Khorezm Region of Uzbekistan, and Tashkhovuz Region of Turkmenistan.

Results and discussion . The results of the 5 first-line drugs of DR showed that 52% of the strains of new patients and 20% of retreatment patients in RCC were fully sensitive to all 5 first-line drugs. In Dashoguz, 70% of strains from new patients and 38% of re-treated patients were susceptible to 5 first-line drugs. In both regions, the most significant monoresistance was recorded against streptomycin (11% of RKK patients and 14% of Dashoguz patients). The highest rate of DR was determined for streptomycin - 58% of all patients in RKK and 37% of patients in Dashoguz. Greater isoniazid resistance was also observed: 53% of patients in RKK and 31% in Dashoguz were infected with resistant strains. Rifampicin resistance was closely related to MDR. These studies showed high rates of MDR in regions of two Central Asian countries.

Regional studies conducted in the Republic of Uzbekistan showed that the prevalence of MDR tuberculosis among newly diagnosed patients is 23 percent, and among relapsers is 62 percent. The results of the DOTS strategy showed failure of first-line treatment in some patients. In 2002, studies were conducted on DR of regional strains. A high rate of MDR tuberculosis was detected in RKK. 13% of patients who have never been treated for TB are infected with the MDR strain [3].

For the past two decades, Médecins Sans Frontières (MSF) has supported RKK's program for TB control, prevention and care for TB patients. The care delivery model focuses on the rapid diagnosis of TB and the identification of drug-resistant agents, which allows for the implementation of effective treatment regimens. A long-term investment in laboratory services has enabled the establishment of a regional laboratory providing phenotypic and genotypic diagnostic tests.

Mycobacterium tuberculosis make it possible to see the strains that pose the greatest risk. Information on the Republic of Uzbekistan shows that regional strains in this regard are poorly studied and require more detailed research. Existing scientific publications mainly cover the clinical aspects and diagnosis of tuberculosis in the region.

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